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THE RURAL SHIFT: DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF GENTRIFICATION IN TENNESSEE COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

As rural communities across the United States deal with rapid social and economic change, the phenomenon of rural gentrification is emerging as a critical area of study, and it remains vastly understudied compared to urban gentrification. This research investigates rural gentrification in Tennessee through tempo-spatial methods, analyzing patterns of demographic shifts, land cover transitions, and property value increases across all 95 counties. In this research, we construct rural gentrification indexes and apply spatial and econometric analyses to assess the displacement of long-time residents and the transformation of rural landscapes. Key drivers such as lifestyle migration and economic development are examined alongside rising costs, land development, and altered community dynamics related factors. Our initial findings highlight non-uniform and evolving spillover effects of urban expansion into rural areas, underscoring the need for policy responses that prioritize affordability, infrastructure sustainability, and cultural preservation. This study not only informs local planning but offers a model for evaluating rural gentrification in other regions undergoing similar transitions

Keywords: Gentrification, Tennessee, Rural